

Platelet-Rich Fibrin Accelerates Wound Healing in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Rats Through Enhanced Collagen Expression

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Highlights

- PRF enhanced the expression of Collagen genes during the healing process.
- Findings suggest PRF as a promising strategy for improving diabetic wound repair.

Abstract

Introduction: Impaired wound healing is a common complication of diabetes mellitus, largely due to chronic inflammation, reduced angiogenesis, and impaired extracellular matrix remodeling. Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF) is a second-generation platelet concentrate rich in growth factors that may enhance tissue regeneration and wound repair. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of PRF on wound healing and collagen gene expression in a diabetic rat model. **Methods:** Diabetes was induced in rats using Streptozotocin (STZ). Full-thickness cutaneous wounds were created on the dorsal surface of the animals. PRF prepared from autologous blood was applied to the wound area in the treatment group, while the control group received standard wound care. Wound healing was assessed by measuring the percentage of wound closure over the experimental period. In addition, the expression of Collagen-related genes in wound tissue was analyzed to evaluate extracellular matrix remodeling. **Results:** PRF treatment significantly accelerated wound closure compared with the control group. Animals treated with PRF showed a higher rate of wound contraction during the observation period. Gene expression analysis also revealed increased collagen expression in the PRF-treated group, suggesting enhanced extracellular matrix deposition and improved tissue repair. **Conclusion:** PRF promotes wound healing in STZ-induced diabetic rats by accelerating wound closure and enhancing collagen gene expression. These findings suggest that PRF may serve as a promising therapeutic approach for improving impaired wound healing associated with diabetes.

Keywords: platelet-rich fibrin, diabetic wound, collagen expression, streptozotocin, wound healing, rat model.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia and multiple systemic complications[1]. One of the most challenging complications is impaired wound healing, which often leads to chronic ulcers and increases the risk of infection and amputation[1]. Diabetic wounds are typically associated with prolonged inflammation, reduced angiogenesis, and impaired extracellular matrix remodeling, all of which contribute to delayed tissue repair. Among extracellular matrix components, Collagen plays a critical role in maintaining tissue integrity and supporting the wound healing process. However, collagen synthesis and deposition are often disrupted under diabetic conditions[2].

Various therapeutic strategies have been investigated to enhance wound healing in diabetic conditions. Recently, autologous platelet concentrates have attracted significant attention in regenerative medicine due to their ability to release multiple growth factors involved in tissue regeneration[3]. Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF), a second-generation platelet concentrate, contains a fibrin matrix enriched with platelets, leukocytes, and growth factors that can promote cell

proliferation, angiogenesis, and extracellular matrix formation[4]. Compared with earlier platelet preparations, PRF provides a more sustained release of bioactive molecules and has shown promising results in several tissue repair applications[5].

Experimental animal models are widely used to investigate potential therapeutic approaches for diabetic wound healing. One of the most commonly used methods to induce experimental diabetes in rodents involves administration of Streptozotocin (STZ), which selectively damages pancreatic β -cells and results in hyperglycemia. This model has been extensively utilized to mimic impaired wound healing observed in diabetic patients[6].

Despite the increasing use of PRF in regenerative medicine, its potential effects on diabetic wound healing and collagen-related gene expression remain insufficiently explored in experimental models. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the effect of PRF on wound healing in STZ-induced diabetic rats by assessing the rate of wound closure and the expression of collagen-related genes in wound tissue.

Materials and methods

Preparation of Platelet-Rich Fibrin

PRF was prepared from autologous rat blood using a standard centrifugation protocol. Whole rat blood was collected without anticoagulant and immediately centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4 °C. After centrifugation, three layers were formed: the red blood cell layer at the bottom, the fibrin clot in the middle, and platelet-poor plasma at the top. The PRF clot was carefully isolated and used for wound treatment.

Animals

Six male Wistar rats weighing 200-250 g were used in this study. All experimental procedures adhered to the guidelines and protocol of the Animal Experimental Ethics Committee of School of Natural Science, Madawalabu University, Ethiopia (Number 2413-EIC). The animals were housed under standard laboratory conditions at a temperature of 22 ± 2 °C with a 12 h light-dark cycle and were provided with food and water ad libitum. All experimental procedures were carried out in accordance with institutional guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals. Experimental diabetes was induced by a single intraperitoneal injection of Streptozotocin at a dose of 60 mg/kg body weight. The compound was freshly dissolved in citrate buffer (0.1 M, pH 4.5) before administration. Blood glucose levels were measured 72 hours after injection, and rats with fasting blood glucose levels ≥ 250 mg/dL were considered diabetic and included in the experiment. After confirmation of diabetes, the animals were anesthetized and the dorsal area was shaved and disinfected. A full-thickness excisional wound with a diameter of approximately 8 mm was created on the dorsal surface using a sterile biopsy punch. The rats were then randomly divided into two groups (n = 3 per group). The control group received standard wound care without treatment, whereas the treatment group received Platelet-Rich Fibrin applied directly to the wound surface immediately after wound creation. The wounds were left uncovered and monitored throughout the experimental period.

Assessment of Wound Healing

Digital photographs of the wounds were taken at day 0, day 7, and day 14 after surgery. Wound areas were measured using imageJ analysis software, and the percentage of wound closure was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Wound closure (\%)} = (\text{initial wound area} - \text{current wound area}) / \text{initial wound area} \times 100$$

Gene Expression Analysis

At the end of the experimental period, wound tissue samples were harvested for gene expression analysis. Total RNA was extracted from the tissue samples with easy-BLUE™ Total RNA Extraction Kit (inTron, USA). Quantitative real-time PCR was performed to analyze the expression of Collagen-related genes associated with extracellular matrix remodeling during wound healing with Luna Universal One-Step RT-qPCR (New England Biolabs, New England).

Table 1. Primers used for quantitative real-time PCR analysis

Gene	Forward Primer (5'-3')	Reverse Primer (5'-3')	Product Size (bp)	Reference
COL3A1	TTTGGCACAGCAGTCCAATGTA	GACAGATCCCGAGTCGCAGA	121	NM_03208 5.1
GAPDH	GAGAAACCTGCCAAGTATG	GGAGTTGCTGTTGAAGTC	177	NM_00128 9726.1

Statistical Analysis

All data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test to compare differences between groups. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Effect of Platelet-Rich Fibrin on Wound Area Reduction During Diabetic Wound Healing

Changes in wound area were evaluated during the healing period in rats with diabetes induced by Streptozotocin. Wound area was measured at days 0, 7, 14, and 21 after wound creation. Animals treated with Platelet-Rich Fibrin showed a faster reduction in wound area compared with the control group (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effect of Platelet-Rich Fibrin on wound area reduction in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats.

The reduction in wound area was monitored over a 21-day period. At day 7, the PRF-treated group showed a smaller remaining wound area ($67.67 \pm 2.52\%$) compared with the control group ($87.00 \pm 3.00\%$), indicating a faster wound contraction during the early stage of healing. By day 14, the wound area further decreased to $35.67 \pm 4.04\%$ in the PRF-treated group, whereas the control group still exhibited a relatively larger wound area ($64.00 \pm 3.61\%$). Complete wound closure was observed in the PRF-treated group by day 21 (0%), while wounds in the control group remained partially open with an average remaining wound area of $24.67 \pm 2.52\%$. These results suggest that Platelet-Rich Fibrin significantly accelerated wound healing in the diabetic rat model (Figure 1).

Effect of Platelet-Rich Fibrin on COL3A1 Gene Expression During Diabetic Wound Healing

The expression level of Collagen Type III Alpha 1 Chain (COL3A1) was evaluated using quantitative real-time PCR to investigate the effect of Platelet-Rich Fibrin on extracellular matrix remodeling during wound healing. Relative gene expression analysis revealed that the PRF-treated group exhibited significantly higher COL3A1 expression compared with the control group. Specifically, the relative expression level of COL3A1 in the PRF-treated wounds was

2.64 ± 0.32 , whereas the control group showed a baseline level of 1.00 ± 0.12 (**Figure 2**). These results indicate that PRF treatment markedly enhanced collagen type III gene expression in the diabetic wound model.

Figure 2. Relative expression of *COL3A1* in diabetic wound tissue following PRF treatment.

Discussion

Impaired wound healing is a common complication associated with diabetes, characterized by prolonged inflammation, reduced angiogenesis, and impaired extracellular matrix remodeling. In this study, the therapeutic effect of Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF) on diabetic wound healing was evaluated using a rat model induced by Streptozotocin[7]. The results demonstrated that PRF treatment significantly accelerated wound closure and enhanced collagen-related gene expression compared with the untreated control group.

Macroscopic evaluation showed that wounds treated with PRF exhibited a faster reduction in wound area throughout the experimental period. By day 14, the PRF-treated wounds had markedly smaller remaining wound areas compared with those in the control group, and complete wound closure was observed by day 21. These findings suggest that PRF promotes the wound healing process by enhancing tissue contraction and re-epithelialization. Previous studies have also reported that platelet-derived biomaterials can improve wound repair by providing a sustained release of growth factors that stimulate cell migration, angiogenesis, and tissue regeneration[8].

In addition to the macroscopic improvement in wound healing, gene expression analysis revealed that PRF significantly increased the expression of Collagen Type III Alpha 1 Chain (*COL3A1*). Collagen type III is a major component of the extracellular matrix during the early phases of wound healing and plays an important role in the formation of granulation tissue. The observed increase in *COL3A1* expression suggests that PRF may enhance fibroblast activity and promote extracellular matrix deposition in diabetic wounds[9].

The beneficial effects of PRF can be attributed to its fibrin matrix enriched with platelets and leukocytes, which release various bioactive molecules involved in tissue regeneration. These factors may stimulate fibroblast proliferation and collagen synthesis, thereby improving the structural integrity of the healing tissue. The combination of accelerated wound contraction and increased collagen gene expression observed in this study indicates that PRF contributes to both the structural and molecular aspects of wound repair[9, 10].

Although the present study demonstrated promising results, the small sample size may limit the generalizability of the findings. Further studies with larger sample sizes and additional molecular markers are needed to better elucidate the mechanisms underlying PRF-mediated diabetic wound healing.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study demonstrated that Platelet-Rich Fibrin effectively promoted wound healing in a diabetic rat model induced by Streptozotocin. PRF treatment significantly accelerated wound closure and enhanced the expression of Collagen Type III Alpha 1 Chain (COL3A1), indicating improved extracellular matrix formation during the healing process. These findings suggest that PRF may serve as a promising therapeutic strategy for improving impaired wound healing associated with diabetes. Further studies with larger sample sizes and additional molecular markers are needed to better understand the mechanisms underlying PRF-mediated tissue repair.

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Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the clarity, grammar, and readability of the text. The authors carefully reviewed and edited the generated content and take full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

CRediT author statement

Mohammed Khan: Conceptualization; Methodology; Supervision; Writing - Reviewing and Editing. Ranjini Keez: Data curation; Investigation; Formal analysis; Writing - Original draft preparation. Yalaga Rao: Visualization; Validation; Methodology.

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